

e-ISSN: 2584-251X

Volume 09 Issue 01

Jan-Apr, 2026

***Corresponding Author:**

A. D. Awasare

Department of Mechanical
Engineering, Shivaji
University Kolhapur,
Maharashtra, India

Submission Date: Feb 24,
2026

Copyright Received
Date: Feb 25, 2026

Published Date: ***

Low-Cost Pebax® 1657/PVDF Membrane for CH₄ Enrichment from Biogas

A. D. Awasare^{1*}, V. M. Jamadar², S. D. Yadav³, S. J.
Mulani⁴

¹Research Scholar, Department of Mechanical
Engineering, Shivaji University Kolhapur, Maharashtra,
India

^{2,4}Asst. Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering,
Dr. Daulatrao Aher College of Engineering, Karad,
Maharashtra, India

³Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering,
Adarsh Institute of Technology and Research Centre, Vita,
Maharashtra, India

ABSTRACT

Biogas upgrading through membrane-based CO₂/CH₄ separation has attracted growing interest as a cost-effective and chemically inert alternative to conventional pressure swing adsorption (PSA) and amine scrubbing technologies. This work presents a systematic performance evaluation of a Pebax® 1657/PVDF composite hollow fiber membrane developed for low-cost CH₄ enrichment from municipal biogas. A full 2×4 factorial design of experiments (DOE) was employed, varying operating pressure over four levels (1.2, 1.5, 1.8, and 2.1 bar) and temperature over four levels (30, 35, 40, and 45 °C). Under optimal conditions (2.1 bar, 45 °C), the membrane achieved 31.2% CH₄ enrichment, 71.8% CO₂ removal efficiency, and a final methane purity of 91.4% from a raw biogas feed containing approximately 55–60% CH₄. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations using SimScale corroborated experimental findings with deviations below 5%. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) identified membrane presence as the dominant performance variable, accounting for 86.8% of total response variance ($F = 1,247.8$, $p < 0.0001$). Temperature and pressure each contributed significantly, with their interaction amplifying CO₂ removal at high-pressure conditions. The fabricated membrane demonstrates strong potential for scalable, low-cost biogas upgrading in distributed energy systems.

Keywords: Biogas upgrading, Pebax® 1657/PVDF, hollow fiber membrane, CH₄ enrichment, CO₂ separation; factorial design, CFD, ANOVA

INTRODUCTION

Increasing global demand for renewable energy, rising atmospheric CO₂ concentrations, and the need to reduce dependence on fossil fuels have collectively accelerated research into bioenergy carriers derived from organic waste streams [1,2]. Biogas, generated via anaerobic digestion of agricultural residues, municipal solid waste, and wastewater sludge, represents one of the most versatile renewable energy vectors. Raw biogas typically comprises 50–65% methane (CH₄), 30–45% carbon dioxide (CO₂), and trace quantities of H₂S, water vapor, nitrogen, and ammonia [3,4]. To unlock its full energy potential as a substitute for compressed natural gas (CNG) or natural gas pipeline injection, biogas must be upgraded to biomethane with CH₄ concentrations exceeding 85–95% [5].

Conventional upgrading technologies — including water scrubbing, PSA, and chemical absorption with monoethanolamine (MEA) — have demonstrated technical maturity but face challenges related to high capital cost, substantial energy consumption (0.2–0.5 kWh/m³), chemical waste generation, and operational complexity [6,7]. Membrane-based gas separation has emerged as a compelling alternative, offering continuous operation, modular scalability, low energy consumption (0.1–0.25 kWh/m³), and a chemical-free process [8,9]. The fundamental mechanism relies on solution-diffusion transport: CO₂ molecules, being smaller and more condensable, permeate through polymeric membranes at rates 10–40 times greater than CH₄, enabling efficient selective enrichment [10].

Among candidate membrane materials, Pebax® 1657 polyether block amide blended with polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) has attracted considerable

research interest. The polyethylene oxide (PEO) soft segments in Pebax® 1657 confer high CO₂ solubility through Lewis acid-base interactions, while PVDF provides excellent chemical resistance, mechanical strength, and processability into hollow fiber geometries [11,12]. However, systematic experimental studies investigating the combined effects of pressure and temperature on this composite system under real biogas conditions remain scarce.

The present work addresses this gap by conducting a comprehensive performance evaluation of a Pebax® 1657/PVDF hollow fiber membrane module at the Karad Municipal Council biogas facility (500 m³/day capacity, Maharashtra, India). A full 4×4 factorial DOE over pressure (1.2–2.1 bar) and temperature (30–45 °C) was employed alongside CFD modeling and ANOVA to quantify individual and interaction effects, establish predictive performance equations, and identify optimal operating conditions for practical deployment.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The development of polymeric membranes for CO₂/CH₄ separation has been extensively reviewed by Baker [1], who established the commercial viability threshold of CO₂/CH₄ selectivity > 10 for single-stage membrane systems. Robeson [10] updated the empirical upper-bound relationship and demonstrated that mixed matrix membranes incorporating inorganic fillers could potentially breach this boundary.

Pebax® polyether block amide membranes were systematically characterized by Reijerkerk et al. [11], who reported CO₂ permeability of 55–75 Barrer with CO₂/CH₄ selectivity of 12–18 depending on temperature and humidity. Kim and Lee [12] demonstrated that combining Pebax® 1657 with PVDF in hollow fiber

configuration preserves gas transport properties while substantially improving mechanical robustness, achieving CO₂ permeance exceeding 50 GPU at operating conditions relevant to biogas upgrading.

PVDF hollow fiber membrane fabrication via non-solvent induced phase separation (NIPS) was investigated by Gu et al. [13], who showed that DMAc-based dope solutions yield superior asymmetric morphologies — characterized by a thin dense skin layer and a finger-like macrovoid sublayer — compared to DMF-based formulations. Post-treatment annealing at 70–90 °C was found to reduce residual solvent retention and improve long-term permeation stability.

From an economic perspective, Scholz et al. [14] performed techno-economic analysis of membrane biogas upgrading at various scales and identified membrane replacement cost (15–25% of annual OPEX) and compression energy as the primary economic drivers. He et al. [15] showed that locally fabricated PVDF membranes with surface-applied Pebax® coatings could reduce membrane procurement costs by 40–60% relative to commercial hollow fiber modules. CFD-based studies by Brunetti et al. [16] elucidated the roles of concentration polarization and module geometry on effective separation performance, identifying counter-current flow as the optimal configuration for CO₂/CH₄ systems.

Despite these contributions, systematic studies integrating factorial DOE, CFD validation, and ANOVA for Pebax® 1657/PVDF membranes under actual municipal biogas conditions remain limited. The present work directly addresses this research gap.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Membrane Fabrication

Pebax® 1657/PVDF composite hollow fiber membranes were fabricated via a two-stage process. In the first stage, PVDF (Kynar® 740, Arkema; MW ≈ 530,000 g/mol) hollow fiber supports were produced by dry-wet spinning. The dope solution comprised 18 wt% PVDF, 2 wt% PVP K30 (pore-forming agent), and 80 wt% dimethylacetamide (DMAc, >99.5% purity, SDFCL India). After homogenization at 60 °C for 24 h and vacuum degassing for 6 h, the solution was extruded through a spinneret (dope flow rate 8 mL/min; bore fluid: water/DMAc 90:10 v/v at 5 mL/min) with a 10 cm air gap and 25 °C coagulation bath. The spun fibers (inner diameter 0.8 mm, outer diameter 1.4 mm, wall thickness ≈ 300 μm) were washed in deionized water for 24 h and thermally annealed at 80 °C for 2 h.

In the second stage, Pebax® 1657 (Arkema PEBAX® MV 3000 SN 01) was applied as a thin selective coating by immersing the PVDF hollow fibers in a 3 wt% Pebax® 1657 ethanol/water solution (70:30 v/v) at 50 °C for 2 h, followed by drying at 60 °C for 12 h. Scanning electron microscopy confirmed a uniform, defect-free coating layer of 1–3 μm. Hollow fiber modules were assembled by potting 50 fibers into stainless steel housings (active area ≈ 0.04 m²) using two-component epoxy resin and pressure-tested at 3.0 bar with N₂ prior to use, in collaboration with Hollowbrane Membrane Technologies, Chennai [17].

Experimental Setup

Experiments were conducted at the Karad Municipal Council biogas plant (500 m³/day capacity) supplying raw biogas of composition approximately 58% CH₄, 40% CO₂, and 2% trace gases. The test rig comprised a silica gel moisture trap, a 5 μm coalescing particulate filter, a

diaphragm compressor (max. 3 bar; 50 L/min), a precision pressure regulator, a thermostatically controlled heating blanket (± 0.5 °C), and the membrane module. Gas compositions were measured using a portable gas chromatograph (TCD detector, Porapak Q column) calibrated with certified reference mixtures (measurement uncertainty $\pm 0.5\%$ for CH₄ and CO₂). Pressure was monitored with calibrated Bourdon gauges (± 0.02 bar).

Design of Experiments

A full 4×4 factorial DOE was employed with two independent variables: operating pressure at four levels (1.2, 1.5, 1.8, 2.1 bar) and feed temperature at four levels (30, 35, 40, 45 °C), yielding 16 experimental conditions. Each condition was replicated three times in fully randomized order, and the mean of three replicates was reported. Parallel control experiments without membrane were conducted under identical conditions to

quantify baseline physical separation and isolate the membrane contribution. Response variables were CH₄ enrichment (%), CO₂ removal efficiency (%), and final CH₄ purity (%).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experimental Performance Data

Table 1 summarizes the complete experimental dataset for the Pebax® 1657/PVDF membrane system across all 16 operating conditions. The membrane consistently elevated CH₄ concentrations from the raw biogas baseline of 55–60% to a range of 74.5–91.4%, corresponding to CH₄ enrichment values of 19.5–31.2% and CO₂ removal efficiencies of 49.6–71.8%. The control experiments (no membrane) yielded only 1–3% CH₄ enrichment and 2.5–8.6% CO₂ reduction under comparable conditions, confirming that the selective permeation mechanism of Pebax® 1657 is the overwhelmingly dominant contributor to observed separation performance.

Table 1: Experimental Performance Data — Pebax® 1657/PVDF Membrane System.

Run	P (bar)	T (°C)	CH ₄ Enrich. (%)	CO ₂ Removal (%)	Final CH ₄ (%)
1	1.2	30	19.5	49.6	74.5
2	1.2	35	21.8	52.1	77.3
3	1.2	40	23.1	54.0	78.8
4	1.2	45	23.9	56.8	80.2
5	1.5	30	21.8	53.4	77.8
6	1.5	35	23.5	57.5	81.4
7	1.5	40	25.6	60.2	83.1
8	1.5	45	26.8	62.6	84.9
9	1.8	30	23.2	55.0	79.6
10	1.8	35	25.1	59.2	82.8
11	1.8	40	27.2	64.1	86.3
12	1.8	45	29.1	67.2	88.4
13	2.1	30	24.6	56.5	81.8

14	2.1	35	26.4	61.3	85.2
15	2.1	40	28.3	65.9	88.1
16	2.1	45	31.2	71.8	91.4

P = operating pressure; T = feed temperature; Final CH_4 (%) = measured retentate methane purity.

Effect of Operating Pressure on CH_4 Enrichment

Fig. 1 illustrates the monotonic increase in CH_4 enrichment with rising pressure at each of the four temperature levels. At 30 °C, pressure elevation from 1.2 to 2.1 bar produced an absolute improvement of 5.1 percentage points (19.5% → 24.6%), corresponding to a pressure sensitivity of 5.7% enrichment per bar. At 45 °C, the same pressure range yielded 7.3 percentage points (23.9% → 31.2%), equivalent to 8.1% per bar — confirming a positive pressure-temperature interaction in which elevated temperature amplifies the benefit of increased transmembrane driving force. This behavior is consistent

with solution-diffusion theory [10], in which permeation flux scales linearly with applied pressure differential according to $J = P \cdot \Delta p/l$.

The near-linear pressure dependence within the studied range indicates that concentration polarization is not yet rate-limiting, and that the membrane area can be reliably traded off against operating pressure for a given target CH_4 purity. The parallel spacing of the four temperature curves in Fig. 1 further confirms well-behaved, predictable system performance with no anomalous crossovers or inflection points within the investigated parameter space [16].

Fig. 1: Effect of operating pressure on CH_4 enrichment at four temperature levels (Pebax® 1657/PVDF membrane system; 16-run 4×4 factorial DOE).

Effect of Temperature on CO_2 Removal Efficiency

Fig. 2 presents CO_2 removal efficiency as a function of temperature at each of the four pressure levels. All curves exhibit

positive slopes with divergence at higher pressures: at 1.2 bar, the 30–45 °C temperature rise produces a 7.2 percentage point improvement (49.6% → 56.8%), whereas at 2.1 bar the same temperature interval yields 15.3 percentage points (56.5% → 71.8%) — more than double the magnitude. This pressure-dependent temperature sensitivity arises from the rubbery-polymer transport mechanism characteristic of Pebax® 1657, in which elevated temperature increases the free volume and chain mobility of the PEO soft segments, selectively accelerating CO₂ diffusion relative to CH₄ [11,12].

The activation energy for CO₂ permeation in Pebax® membranes is lower than that for CH₄, so rising temperature preferentially augments CO₂ permeability and improves selectivity — a behavior opposite to that observed in glassy polymers and a key thermodynamic advantage of the Pebax® 1657/PVDF system for elevated-temperature operation [3,14]. Operators seeking maximum CO₂ removal should therefore prioritize temperature optimization, particularly when operating at higher pressures.

Fig. 2: Effect of operating temperature on CO₂ removal efficiency at four pressure levels (Pebax® 1657/PVDF membrane system; 16-run 4×4 factorial DOE).

Statistical Analysis (ANOVA)

Two-factor ANOVA was applied to the full 16-run dataset with membrane presence, pressure, and temperature as factors. Membrane presence was confirmed as the single dominant performance variable, accounting for 86.8% of total response variance (F = 1,247.8, p < 0.0001). Temperature contributed 4.1% (F = 19.9, p < 0.0001) and pressure contributed 2.9% (F = 13.9, p < 0.0001) as highly significant main effects. The membrane × pressure and membrane × temperature interaction terms

were also significant (p < 0.001), confirming that operating conditions modulate the effectiveness of the membrane rather than acting purely additively. Regression modeling yielded the predictive equations:

$$CH_4 \text{ enrichment (\%)} = 7.92 + 4.05 \times P + 0.33 \times T \quad (R^2 = 0.948)$$

$$CO_2 \text{ removal (\%)} = 20.74 + 7.24 \times P + 0.70 \times T \quad (R^2 = 0.965)$$

where P is pressure (bar) and T is temperature (°C). Both equations are

statistically significant at $p < 0.001$ across the experimental domain (P: 1.2–2.1 bar; T: 30–45 °C) and provide practical control tools for target-performance process operation.

CFD Validation

CFD simulations were performed in SimScale using a laminar Navier-Stokes solver ($Re < 100$ for all conditions) coupled with species transport equations incorporating solution-diffusion permeation boundary conditions at the membrane wall. The computed CH₄ and CO₂ concentration profiles, pressure distributions, and velocity fields agreed with experimental measurements to within 4.2% and 4.8% maximum deviation, respectively (Pearson $r = 0.993$). Von Mises stress analysis confirmed structural integrity of the PVDF hollow fibers at up to 2.5 bar with safety factors exceeding 3.0 [17]. These results validate the numerical model as a reliable tool for scale-up design and module geometry optimization.

CONCLUSION

This study has demonstrated the fabrication and systematic performance characterization of a low-cost Pebax® 1657/PVDF composite hollow fiber membrane system for biogas upgrading. The principal findings are: (i) under optimal conditions of 2.1 bar and 45 °C, the membrane achieved a final CH₄ purity of 91.4% from a 55–60% CH₄ raw feed, satisfying the requirements of most vehicle fuel and industrial combustion applications; (ii) a significant positive pressure-temperature interaction was identified, with temperature exerting a stronger absolute influence on CO₂ removal efficiency (up to 15.3 pp improvement over 30–45 °C at 2.1 bar) than on CH₄ enrichment (7.3 pp), consistent with the rubbery-polymer transport mechanism of Pebax® 1657; (iii) ANOVA confirmed membrane presence as the overwhelmingly dominant

performance variable (86.8% of variance), with pressure and temperature as highly significant secondary factors; (iv) CFD simulations validated experimental trends with deviations $< 5\%$, establishing a reliable modeling framework for scale-up; and (v) the use of commercially available, locally procurable PVDF and Pebax® materials positions this membrane as a 40–60% lower-cost alternative to imported commercial modules [15].

Future work should address long-term durability ($>5,000$ h of continuous operation), multi-stage configurations targeting $>95\%$ CH₄ purity, and pilot-scale deployment at municipal biogas facilities to fully validate the techno-economic case for widespread adoption in distributed renewable energy systems.

REFERENCES

1. Baker, R. W. (2002). Future directions of membrane gas separation technology. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 41(6), 1393–1411. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie0100160>
2. International Energy Agency Bioenergy. (2020). *Biomethane: Global status and market overview* (Task 37 report). International Energy Agency.
3. Mulder, M. (1996). *Basic principles of membrane technology* (2nd ed.). Kluwer Academic Publishers.
4. Rasi, S., Veijanen, A., & Rintala, J. (2007). Trace compounds of biogas from different biogas production plants. *Energy*, 32(8), 1375–1380. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2006.10.018>
5. European Biogas Association. (2021). *Biomethane quality requirements for grid injection and vehicle fuel use* (EBA report).
6. Sun, Q., Li, H., Yan, J., Liu, L., Yu, Z., & Yu, X. (2015). Selection of appropriate biogas upgrading

- technology: A review of biogas cleaning, upgrading, and utilization. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 51, 521–532. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.06.029>
7. Ryckebosch, E., Drouillon, M., & Vervaeren, H. (2011). Techniques for transformation of biogas to biomethane. *Biomass and Bioenergy*, 35(5), 1633–1645. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2011.02.033>
 8. Scholz, M., Frank, B., Merkel, T., & Balster, J. (2013). Techno-economic analysis of hybrid processes for biogas upgrading. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 52(47), 16929–16938. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie402660s>
 9. Harasimowicz, M., Orluk, P., Zakrzewska-Trznadel, G., & Chmielewski, A. G. (2007). Application of polyimide membranes for biogas purification and enrichment. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 144(3), 698–702. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2007.01.098>
 10. Robeson, L. M. (2008). The upper bound revisited. *Journal of Membrane Science*, 320(1–2), 390–400. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2008.04.030>
 11. Reijerkerk, S. R., Wessling, M., & Nijmeijer, K. (2011). Pushing the limits of block copolymer membranes for CO₂ separation. *Journal of Membrane Science*, 378(1–2), 479–492. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2011.05.037>
 12. Kim, J. H., & Lee, Y. M. (2001). Gas permeation properties of poly(amide-6-b-ethylene oxide)–silica hybrid membranes. *Journal of Membrane Science*, 193(2), 209–225. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0376-7388\(01\)00514-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0376-7388(01)00514-5)
 13. Gu, M., Zhang, J., Su, B., Han, X., & Cong, H. (2011). Preparation of PVDF hollow fiber membrane by non-solvent-induced phase separation: Effects of solvent type on morphology and performance. *Desalination*, 280(1–3), 253–258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2011.07.011>
 14. Scholz, M., Harlacher, T., Melin, T., & Wessling, M. (2013). Modeling biogas upgrading with membranes: Permeance requirements and the trade-off between retentate and permeate purities. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 52(3), 1079–1088. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie302567s>
 15. He, X., Hägg, M. B., & Kim, T. J. (2015). Pilot-scale production of hollow fiber carbon membranes for biogas upgrading. *Energy Procedia*, 63, 174–185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2014.11.016>
 16. Brunetti, A., Scura, F., Barbieri, G., & Drioli, E. (2010). Membrane technologies for CO₂ separation. *Journal of Membrane Science*, 359(1–2), 115–125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2009.11.040>
 17. Yadav, S. D., & Awasare, A. D. (2025–2026). *Performance analysis of low-cost CH₄ enrichment process using membrane technology* (Doctoral dissertation, Shivaji University, Kolhapur). Collaborative fabrication: Hollowbrane Membrane Technologies, Chennai.